

Studies on the Effect of Binder on Membrane Properties of Ferric Hydroxide Gel

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The effect of polystyrene binder concentration on the membrane properties (such as porosity, membrane conductance and membrane potential of ferric hydroxide gel) has been studied. The results show that porosity and membrane conductance depend upon the percentage of the binder. Porosity is almost negligible when the amount of binder exceeds 45%. The membrane conductance varies with ionic form of the gel in the order: $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$ and $\text{Ba}^{++} < \text{Ca}^{++} < \text{Mg}^{++}$. The electrochemical performance of the membranes in moderately concentrated electrolyte solutions is independent of the binder percentage from 15 to 30%.

HETEROGENEOUS membranes offer a much greater variety for fundamental and applied studies than the homogeneous ones¹. The former consists of colloidal ion-exchanger particles coated with or embedded in an inert substrate or binder compatible with the required mechanical strength. A necessary requirement for such membranes is that the ion-exchanger particles should remain in contact with one another rather than be separated by the inert material. The percentage of the inert material plays an important role in characterising the membrane behaviour.

Our present communication deals with the role of the binder (polystyrene) on the membrane properties like porosity, membrane conductance and membrane potential of ferric hydroxide gel.

Experimental

Preparation of Membrane: Polystyrene supported ferric hydroxide membrane was prepared by heating gradually to 1150°, 1.5 g of homogenised (<200 mesh size) mixture of ferric hydroxide gel and polystyrene (4 : 1) in a die (2.5 cm diameter) of the specimen mount press and subsequently cooling down to room temperature under pressure ranging between 6500 and 7500 psi²⁻³. Membranes (0.1 cm to 0.15 cm thick) containing varying amounts of binder (15 to 45%) were prepared in this way in order to investigate the effect of binder on membrane behaviour.

Determination of Porosity: The membranes with different gel-binder ratio were abraded with a fine glass paper, weighed and then immersed in 1-2M NaCl for 24 hours. The membranes were washed several times with deionised water, the adhering liquid was wiped out with blotting paper and then weighed in a stoppered bottle. Later on they were

dried at 110° in a vacuum desiccator and weighed. The difference between the two weighings divided by the weight of the wet membrane was taken as water content. The porosity of the membrane was calculated by formula⁴:

$$\xi = \frac{\text{Water content}}{A \times L \times dw}$$

where, A = Area of membrane, L = thickness of membrane and dw = density of water.

Conductance Measurements: The method recommended by Lakshminarayanaiah⁵ was employed for this purpose. The membrane in the requisite cationic form was cemented between the two half cells with the help of an adhesive (Araldite). It was then equilibrated by filling the half cell with 0.05 M metal chloride solution. The solution was then replaced with mercury which had been previously equilibrated with the same metal chloride solution. The conductance was measured by connecting the platinum electrodes in the two limbs of the cell to the conductivity bridge working at 3 Kc/s.

Potential Measurements: Michaelis's⁶ method was used to determine the membrane potential using the cell:

SCE/solution (C₁)/Membrane/Solution (C₂)/SCE
where C₁/C₂ = 10.

Results and Discussion

When a heterogeneous membrane is immersed in water or electrolyte solution, swelling takes place and the solution penetrates into the membrane structure occupying interstices which are already

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present or which develop as a result of the difference between the volume of membrane material and that of the binder. The interstices act as a film and diffusion of electrolytes become possible also by film diffusion besides the normal diffusion through the membrane material. In some cases swelling results in the permeation of impermeable species. The amount of water incorporated in the membrane structure varies with the percentage of binder used in the membrane and it goes on decreasing when the amount of binder is increased. This suggests that in membranes containing higher proportions of polystyrene complete swelling of the gel is not obtained either as a result of mechanical restraint imposed by the binder or because some of the gel is inaccessible to water. Therefore, when the percentage of the binder is increased the role of binder is to cause a decrease in porosity which almost becomes negligible when the amount of binder is more than 45% (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of binder on porosity of ferric hydroxide membrane (sodium form).

The conductance measurements show that the value of membrane conductance changes initially very slowly with time but becomes constant after 10 to 15 minutes and remains so for nearly 4 to 5 hours after which it changes slightly.

The data given in Table 1 show that the sequence of membrane conductance for the various alkali cations is $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$ and $\text{Ba}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Mg}^{2+}$ for alkaline earth cations. The behaviour is similar to that observed by George⁷ and Lakshminarayaniah⁸. The lower values of conductance for

Fig. 2. Effect of binder on specific conductance of ferric hydroxide membrane (sodium form).

bivalent cations as compared to monovalent cations show that as the charge on the counter ion is increased the membrane conductance gets decreased.

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE OF FERRIC HYDROXIDE MEMBRANE (WITH 20% BINDER) IN DIFFERENT CATIONIC FORMS (in mhos)

Electrolytic form	Li^+	Na^+	K^+	Rb^+	Cs^+	Ba^{2+}	Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
Specific conductance	6.5×10^{-3}	10.5×10^{-3}	21.5×10^{-3}	32.5×10^{-3}	96.5×10^{-3}	9.1×10^{-4}	9.88×10^{-4}	12.9×10^{-4}

This may be ascribed to increase ion association of the diffusing ions with the membrane exchange sites. The low values of membrane conductance in this case may be explained as follows :

When the membrane is equilibrated with 0.05 M metal chloride, the interstices which are already present or formed by swelling of the gel particles retain the electrolyte solution. The absorbed solution alongwith the counter ions carries the charge. The presence of these interstices may facilitate the passage of ions through the membrane from one particle to another. Gregor⁸ suggested that a thin film of water between the gel particles and binder may also provide a pathway through the membrane for ions and water. The extent of interstices formed in case of ferric hydroxide membrane is very low and this results in poor electrolyte absorption giving rise to low conductance values. Thus, it is concluded that the conductance developed in the membrane phase is due to the combined effect of the counter ions and absorbed electrolytes.

The effect of increasing binder to gel ratio is to decrease interstitial volume which results in lower electrolyte absorption giving rise to a low value of conductance.

No appreciable effect of the binder concentration on membrane potential could be observed in the range 15 to 30% as is evident from the data given in Table 2. It may, therefore, be concluded that the π electrons of the binder do not affect the electrochemical performance of the exchanger at least in moderately concentrated solutions.

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TABLE 2—POTENTIALS OF FERRIC HYDROXIDE MEMBRANE HAVING VARYING AMOUNTS OF BINDER

Inside solution conc. of KCl	Observed membrane potentials in membrane with varying amount of binder				
	Outside solution conc. of KCl	15%	20%	25%	30%
1.0M/0.1M		32.5	32.5	32.6	32.7
0.5/0.05		35.7	35.8	35.9	36.0
0.2/0.02		38.2	38.1	38.2	38.1
0.1/0.01		40.6	40.4	40.5	40.6
0.05/0.005		41.3	41.3	41.4	41.4
0.02/0.002		41.7	41.8	41.9	42.0
0.02/0.001		42.7	42.7	42.9	43.0
0.005/0.0005		43.6	43.7	44.0	43.9